

MATRIX MICROCRACKING DAMAGE CHARACTERIZATION OF DISCONTINUOUS CARBON FIBER REINFORCED GLASS-MATRIX COMPOSITES

N. TAKEDA*, O. CHEN*, T. KISHI* and K. PREWO**

* Research Center for Advanced Science and Technology, The University of Tokyo
4-6-1 Komaba, Meguro-ku, Tokyo 153, Japan

** United Technologies Research Center, East Hartford, Connecticut 06108, U.S.A.

ABSTRACT

A high compliant, high failure strain glass matrix composite can be achieved by randomly-oriented discontinuous carbon fiber reinforcement. A unique non-linear tensile stress-strain behavior is due to the extensive matrix microcracking in this brittle matrix composites during loading. In the present study, matrix microcracking damages are introduced in thermal shock conditions. Thermal-shock damages are microscopically observed using optical and scanning acoustic microscopes to understand the damage development. Tensile stress-strain diagrams are, then, obtained for the above thermal-shock damaged specimens with the detailed acoustic emission measurements. Microscopic damage progress and fracture mechanisms, especially matrix microcracking, are characterized and compared with those of the virgin specimens.

KEYWORDS: Glass Matrix; Graphite (Carbon) Fiber; Short Fiber Composite; Damage Accumulation; Failure Mechanism; Tensile; Acoustic Emission

1. INTRODUCTION

Advanced ceramic or glass materials are being extensively used as high-temperature structural materials. Mechanical or thermal loadings often cause rapid decrease in strength due to the inherent low fracture toughness of these materials. Whisker reinforcement provides some increase in fracture toughness, and actual structures are being developed using these materials. Continuous fiber reinforcement gives much more increase in toughness, but wider applications are presently limited due to difficulty in composite fabrication. Discontinuous fiber reinforcement is an alternative method to obtain high fracture toughness.

Prewo⁽¹⁾ developed such glass matrix composites with two-dimensional randomly-oriented discontinuous carbon fiber reinforcement. These composites exhibited a pronounced non-

linear stress-strain behavior with high failure strain for both uniaxial tensile and flexural loadings. Such characteristic behavior is due to the extensive matrix microcracking during loading. In addition, it was shown that there is a significant difference in tensile and flexural behavior, and an analytical model was established to predict the behavior.⁽²⁾ Acoustic emission (AE) analyses have been also performed to monitor damage initiation and progression during testing to distinguish the fracture mechanisms and to explain the unique stress-strain behavior.⁽³⁾

In the present study, matrix microcracking damages are introduced in thermal shock experiments. Thermal shock behavior is one of the most important design criteria for ceramic or glass materials.⁽⁴⁾ Thermal-shock damages are microscopically observed using optical and scanning acoustic microscopes to understand the damage development. Tensile stress-strain diagrams are, then, obtained for the above thermal-shock damaged specimens with the acoustic emission measurements. Microscopic damage progress and fracture mechanisms, especially matrix microcracking, are characterized and compared with those of the virgin specimens.

2. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Tested Materials The composites were made in three steps. (1) Thin sheets of randomly-oriented discontinuous carbon fiber paper were slurry-infiltrated with glass matrix. Initial fiber length was 19 mm and fibers were individually separated so that the paper consisted of an array of fibers and not fiber bundles. (2) The sheets were laid up parallel and perpendicular to the paper roll axis alternately in order to ensure in-plane quasi-isotropic properties. (3) Composite plates were fabricated in 150 mm x 150 mm x 3 mm size by hot press densification at 6.9 MPa pressure and temperatures above 1200 °C. The constituent material properties are shown in Table 1. The nominal fiber volume fraction was 30 %, and the porosity was 1-3 %.

Two kinds of plates, denoted by #634 and #611, were fabricated using different pressing temperatures. Scanning electron micrographs (SEM) of polished surfaces are shown in Fig. 1. Plate #634 shows more porosity than plate #611, which may be due to the fact that plate #611 was consolidated at a higher temperature. Randomly oriented microcracks on the plate face (perpendicular to the hot pressing direction) could be found in plate #611. The cracks on the edge were less random and mostly perpendicular to the face. No cracks were observed in

TABLE 1 PROPERTIES OF CONSTITUENT MATERIALS

	Density (g/cm ³)	Elastic Modulus (GPa)	Tensile Strength (MPa)	Annealing Point (°C)	Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (10 ⁻⁶ /°C)
Borosilicate Glass	2.23	63	-	560	3.25
Celion Fiber	1.76	350	2700	-	-

(a) Plate #634

(b) Plate #611

Figure 1 SEM Photos of Polished Specimen Surfaces

plate #634. The cracking in plate #611 is also attributed to the use of the higher process temperature.

2.2 Thermal Shock Test Fabricated composite plates were carefully cut with a diamond saw to avoid damage during machining into 150mm x 5 mm x 3mm test specimen size. Plate #634 specimens were heated in air using infrared gold image furnace, from room temperature to prescribed temperatures (550, 620 and 680 °C at the present experiment) at the increasing rate of 50 K/min. Figure 2 shows the thermal shock test setup. Specimens were kept at the prescribed temperature for 20 min to ensure the uniform temperature distribution in the specimens, and then fallen into water (20 °C) to generate thermal shock loading. This provided the thermal shock condition with temperature difference ΔT of 530, 600 and 660 °C.

2.3 Microscopic Observations of Damages The faces and edges of thermal-shocked specimens were carefully polished using diamond pastes of sizes of 9, 6, 3 and 1 μm in that order, and microscopically observed using optical microscopes (OM), SEM, and scanning acoustic microscopes (SAM, Olympus UH-3). In particular, SAM observations are suitable to detect matrix cracking or fiber/matrix debonding even with small crack opening displacement. Matrix microcracking in plate #611 can be also detected by SAM. Surface and subsurface images were obtained with 400 or 800 MHz burst signals. SAM provides an excellent quantitative nondestructive evaluation method for composites, especially for short fiber composites. See Ref. (4) for details.

2.4 Tensile Test and AE Measurement Glass-epoxy end tabs (45 mm long, 20° taper) were adhesively bonded to the ends of the thermal-shocked tensile test specimens. Tensile tests were conducted using a screw driven Instron at a crosshead speed of 0.1 mm/min.

Figure 2 Thermal-Shock Test Setup

Figure 3 Tensile Test and AE Measurement

Longitudinal and transverse strain gages (5 mm and 2 mm long, respectively) were mounted on one face of each tensile specimen. A personal computer-based data acquisition system was used to obtain digital stress-strain data, while AE signals from the specimen were monitored simultaneously (Fig. 3). A PAC 3000/3104 AE system with small wide-band AE sensors (PAC pico) was used to acquire and analyze the AE data during monotonic tensile loading. A two-channel mode was used with two sensors 40 mm apart. A well-controlled signal was used to calibrate the sensors. A preamplifier gain of 40 dB, a main gain of 20 dB, a threshold of 0.1 volts and a dead time of 0 μ s were selected for data acquisition. The AE data obtained during testing were post analyzed using a location filtering to eliminate noise signals. Only the signals from the center 20 mm region were selected, using the arrival time difference method.

3. EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

3.1 Thermal Shock-Induced Damage Observations Optical micrographs of matrix cracks generated by thermal shock of temperature difference ΔT of 530 $^{\circ}$ C are shown in Fig. 4. These matrix cracks can be detected only near specimen surfaces and almost randomly distributed two-dimensionally. Higher ΔT increases the crack density, resulting in lower initial Young's modulus and different stress-strain behavior, as will be shown later. SAM observations can often detect matrix cracking or fiber/matrix debonding even with small crack opening displacement. Figure 5 shows subsurface images of typical matrix cracks detected by SAM. When the focal depth z is smaller than 0 (subsurface images can be obtained), cracks can be detected by multiple interference fringes parallel to the crack length. Incident acoustic waves generate Rayleigh surface waves on specimen surfaces, which are reflected at crack surfaces. These waves and the normal waves reflected from the focal depth are, then, interfered with each other to generate the multiple fringes.⁽⁶⁾ Cracks with the maximum depth

of 250 μm were detected in this sample. Enlarged view of matrix cracking is shown in Fig. 6. There also exist some fiber/matrix debondings in other specimens.

(a) Planar View

(b) Sectional View

Figure 4 Optical Micrographs of Thermal-Shock Generated Matrix Cracking ($\Delta T = 530^\circ\text{C}$)

(a) Planar View

(b) Sectional View

Figure 5 SAM Photos of Thermal-Shock Generated Matrix Cracking ($\Delta T = 530^\circ\text{C}$)
 $f = 400 \text{ MHz}$, $z = -3 \mu\text{m}$. Matrix cracks can be detected by ultrasonic interference fringes, even if the crack opening displacement is small.

(a) $z = -3.5 \mu\text{m}$

(b) $z = -5 \mu\text{m}$

Figure 6 Enlarged SAM View of Matrix Cracking ($f = 800 \text{ MHz}$)

3.2 Tensile Test and AE Measurement Results

A tensile stress-strain curve of a thermal-shocked plate #634 specimen ($\Delta T = 600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) is shown in Fig. 7, and compared with those of virgin plate #611 and #634 specimens without thermal-shock damages. Virgin plate #634 specimens exhibit a characteristic non-linear stress-strain curve, which can be divided into the following three stages: (a) linear elastic stage with initial Young's modulus of 44.6 GPa, (b) plateau or pseudo-"yielding" stage after 0.1 % strain due to extensive matrix cracking (normal to tensile direction and through the width), where a large amount of longitudinal strain is produced with little increase in the stress, and (c) almost linear stage after 0.4 % strain with reduced modulus (16.9 GPa prior to failure). On the other hand, three distinct stages cannot be observed in the stress-strain curve for virgin plate #611 specimens, and only a "knee" region between 0.1 and 0.2 % strain is found. The modulus is 35.1 GPa in the initial region, and decreases to 20.3 GPa in the final region. This can be attributed to the pre-existing matrix cracking in plate #611 in as-fabricated condition. The thermal-shocked plate #634 specimen ($\Delta T = 600\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) has an initial modulus of 35.4 MPa, which is similar to that of the virgin plate #611 specimen. Figure 8 shows the effects of ΔT on stress-strain behavior. A noticeable difference is observed between curves at 550 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and at 620 (or 680) $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which indicates a change in damage extent.

Figure 7 Comparison of Tensile Stress-Strain Curves of Plate #611 and #634 (With and Without Thermal Shock)

Figure 9 indicates cumulative AE events against longitudinal strain during tensile tests. Similar AE characteristics were obtained at different ΔT , so only the 530 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ result is shown here. AE amplitude distributions at different load levels are shown in Figs. 10-12. An optical micrograph of matrix cracking after the tensile test of thermal-shocked plate #634 ($\Delta T = 530\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) is shown in Fig. 13, which shows the coalescence of thermal shock-induced matrix cracks.

Figure 8 Effects of Temperature Difference ΔT on Stress-Strain Curves of Plate #634

Figure 9 Cumulative AE Events against Longitudinal Strain

Figure 10 AE Amplitude Distributions for Plate #634 at Different Load Levels (Without Thermal Shock)

Figure 11 AE Amplitude Distributions for Plate #611 at Different Load Levels (Without Thermal Shock)

Figure 12 AE Amplitude Distributions for Thermal-Shocked Plate #634 at Different Load Levels ($\Delta T = 530^\circ\text{C}$)

Figure 13 Optical Micrograph of Matrix Cracking after Tensile Test of Thermal-Shocked Plate #634 ($\Delta T = 530^\circ\text{C}$)

4. DISCUSSION

The plate #634 specimen thermal-shocked with $\Delta T = 530^\circ\text{C}$ has some surface matrix cracks, but there exist three distinct stages and an initial modulus is similar to that of the virgin plate #634. Finite element calculation of transient thermal stresses gives the maximum stress of 32 MPa,⁽⁷⁾ which is above 27 MPa as a matrix crack initiation stress obtained in tensile tests of virgin plate #634 specimens. The specimens thermal-shocked with $\Delta T = 600$ and 660°C , on the other hand, have much lower initial moduli. Final failure strain and strength are also reduced. This indicates that there exists a threshold ΔT_c between 550 and 600°C . Thermal shock-induced matrix cracking is confined in near-surface layers, but the crack density increases rapidly above ΔT_c , resulting in much decrease in both modulus and strength. A preliminary SAM measurement of surface wave speeds shows an appreciable decrease after matrix crack initiation induced by thermal shock. Decrease in surface wave speeds is anticipated to be related with the increase in crack density. A quantitative evaluation is now in progress.

Cumulative AE events against longitudinal strain (Fig. 9) corresponds to the initiation and/or progression of matrix cracks. These results for thermal-shocked plate #634 specimens are

similar to those for virgin plate #611 specimens, not for virgin plate #634 ones, which is also true in stress-strain behavior. (It should be noted that the stress at AE initiation is almost the same, but the corresponding strain is quite different.) Cumulative AE events increase monotonically in both thermal-shocked plate #634 specimens and virgin plate #611 specimens. In virgin plate #634 specimens, on the other hand, AE event rates are once reduced when matrix cracks are saturated, and then increase again before final failure.

Similarity of thermal-shocked plate #634 specimens and virgin plate #611 specimens also holds true in AE amplitude distributions. That is, AE amplitudes in Fig. 12 are 40-65 dB at all stages except near the final failure stage, and similar to those in Fig. 11, not in Fig. 10. Larger amplitudes of 60-80 dB are detected at the corresponding stages in Fig. 10. It is expected that growth and coalescence of randomly-distributed existing matrix cracks generate small-amplitude AE signals in both thermal-shocked plate #634 specimens and virgin plate #611 specimens. It is also anticipated that matrix crack initiation and growth through the width and normal to tensile direction generate large-amplitude AE signals in virgin plate #634 specimens. This explains the difference in amplitude distributions. Replicas of specimen surfaces taken during tensile loading confirmed the above crack growth behavior.

5. CONCLUSIONS

Matrix microcracking damage characterization was conducted in a high compliant, high failure strain glass matrix composite with randomly-oriented discontinuous carbon fiber reinforcement. Extensive matrix microcracking during loading provided a unique non-linear tensile stress-strain behavior. In the present study, matrix microcracking damages were introduced in thermal shock conditions. Thermal-shock damages were microscopically observed using optical and scanning acoustic microscopes to understand the damage development. Tensile stress-strain diagrams were, then, obtained for the above thermal-shock damaged specimens with the detailed acoustic emission measurements. Microscopic damage progress and fracture mechanisms, especially matrix microcracking, were characterized and compared with those of the virgin specimens with and without pre-existing matrix cracks.

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